

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D8.2- SOILDIVERAGRO WEBSITE

Universidade de Vigo

D8.2. SOILDIVERAGRO WEBSITE

Summary

When conducting a research project, a key point is the development of methods that will be used to deliver the results and all important information to the general public. In order to communicate and disseminate information and results of the **SoildiverAgro**, a project website has been developed: www.soildiveragro.eu.

This deliverable summarizes the information available on that website, which includes basic data about the project (objectives, work packages, impact, financing and copyright issues), the workgroups, the experiments that will be carried out (including case studies), information about related projects, press appearances. In addition, the website will serve as a repository for documents that are generated as the project progresses (deliverables, reports, minutes, etc.). The website also includes contact details and links to the social networks of the project (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube and Facebook), and will include a Decision Support Tool that is going to be created to improve the efficiency of agriculture.

Deliverable Number		Work Package	
D8.2.		WP8_Communication, dissemination, exploitation and stakeholders engagement	
Lead Beneficiary		Deliverable Author(s)	
Uvigo		David Fernández Calviño [UVIGO] Diego Soto Gómez [UVIGO]	
Versions (updates)		Date	
V1.0		25.11.2019	
V2.0		27.11.2019	
Deliverable Quality Check		Date	
David Fernández Calviño [Uvigo]		29.11.2019	
Planned Delivery Date		Final Delivery Date	
30.11.2019		30.11.2019	
Type of deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	X
	E	Ethycs	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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1 Introduction

Nowadays, a website is a fundamental tool used to communicate results to a broad audience. The website will disseminate the progress in the **SoildiverAgro** project from the start. In this web, by using a tool that is going to be updated periodically, the members of the project will include information about international events (conferences, workshops), technical publications and conferences, newsletters and local events (training courses, seminars, talks, workshops, field days, press releases, etc.).

On the website a Decision Support Tool (DST) will also be available. It is a web-based application that will allow the farmers to identify the most efficient cropping system adapted to their crop and pedoclimatic region. This tool is intended to improve the efficient use of the products employed in agriculture and to reduce the use of some of them (e.g. fungicides).

Moreover, the website will also be used as a repository for all the information produced during the development of the project (deliverables, reports, minutes, etc.). Finally, the website will include contact information and links to the SoildiverAgro social networks (Youtube, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn).

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2 Web Structure: Home

The **SoildiverAgro** project website will be divided into the following sections:

- Home
- Project
- Team
- Our Work
- Repository
- News
- Related Projects

After opening the page, the browser takes us by default to the home page (see Figure 1). This part of the website includes only the title of the website and the acronym.

Figure 1: Home page.

In the upper part of the page a language selection tool can be found, and in the bottom, the links to the social media are included: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Youtube (from left to right).

2.1 Project

The Project tab is divided into:

- Objectives, a section that includes the main goals of the **SoildiverAgro** project.
- Work Packages, a section that contains information about each work package and its objectives.
- Impacts, a section that includes the expected impacts of the **SoildiverAgro** and the measures used to maximize that impact.
- Funding, an overview of the financial resources received to develop the project.
- Disclaimer and copyright, a section that includes information of the privacy policy, copyright and other legal information

When clicking in the Project tab, a dropdown list will appear offering the available contents of the section, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Contents of the Project tab.

When selecting one of the options of the displayed list, the user will have access to the content desired. For example, if someone clicks on the objectives section, the information about the goals of the project will be presented (Figure 3). The index that includes the sections of the web will be displayed on the right part of the page. The new window will show (under the title of the section) the exact position of the user in the web: Home/Project/Objectives/ (Figure 3).

OBJECTIVES

Home / Project / Objectives

The specific objectives of Soildiver Agro are:

1. To identify the main **agricultural challenges** threatening soil biodiversity for key European crops through strong **involvement of stakeholders and end-users** to ensure a realistic identification of farmers' and social challenges.
2. To **expand the knowledge about the soil micro- and macro-organisms' genetic and functional diversity** and their dynamics in representative European croplands under both different production systems (conventional and organic) and management practices across 9 European pedoclimatic regions (86% EU-28 territory), and to assess the relationships among soil biodiversity, agricultural production, soil characteristics, climatic conditions and cropping systems (WP3).
3. To contribute to the ongoing development of **protocols to assess, evaluate, monitor and operationally define soil genetic and functional biodiversity** (micro- and macro-organisms) (WP4).
4. To identify key target **micro- and macro-organisms and to assess the interactions between soil organisms genetic and functional diversity** and i) plant health, ii) plant growth and development, iii) crop yield and quality, iv) reduction of external inputs (water, pesticides, fertilizers, fuel...), and v) the delivery of other ecosystem services (soil fertility, prevention of soil pollution,

Home
Project
Objectives
Work Packages
Impacts
Funding
Disclaimer and copyright

Figure 3: Objectives of the project.

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2.2 Team

The Team tab, as can be seen in Figure 4, is divided into Partners, Coordination board, and Advisory Board; Each section summarizes information about the members of these three parts.

Figure 4: Contents of the Team tab.

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2.3 Our Work

The Our Work tab, as can be seen in Figure 5, is divided into Case Studies and Background. The Case Studies section includes information about the 15 field case studies established. The Background part includes general data of subjects related to the **SoildiverAgro** project.

Figure 5: Contents of the Our Work tab.

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2.4 Repository, News and Related Projects

The remaining tabs, Repository and, News and Related Projects (Figure 1), are not divided into subsections.

The web will be used as a Repository and will contain relevant documents of the project. This can be found in the Repository tab.

The News tab will include references of the project in the Press.

There is also a section, the Related Projects tab, that includes information about similar projects.